

A Caveat on the Application of Simultaneous Inference of Relative Gene Expressions in RNA Sequencing Data Analysis

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Abstract

In RNA sequencing data analysis, Li (2020) proposed a simultaneous inference method to identify differentially expressed genes based on Poisson generalized linear models. In this article, we provide a caveat through a Monte Carlo simulation study on the application of the simultaneous inference method.

Key Words: Simultaneous Confidence Intervals, Simultaneous Tests, Parametric Bootstrap Method

1. Introduction

A major challenge in gene expression analysis is to control the familywise error rate (*FWER*), the probability of identifying at least one mis-expressed gene(s) under the complete null hypothesis. Dudoit *et al* (2003) give an expository overview of the multiple comparison methods in microarray gene expression analysis. In RNA sequencing gene expression analysis, Li (2020) proposed a simultaneous inference method based on parametric bootstrapping to identify differentially expressed genes, when data fit Poisson generalized linear models. In this article, we overview this method and provide a caveat, where it can be conservative in multiple comparisons. We conduct a Monte Carlo simulation based on a real example for illustration.

2. Overview of the Simultaneous Inference Method for Gene Expressions

Assume that the independent observation Y_{ijk} is the number of RNA sequence copies of gene l from the i -th treatment, the j -th block, and the k -th replicate, $i = 1, \dots, a$, $j = 1, \dots, b$, $k = 1, \dots, n_{ij}$, and $l = 1, \dots, g$ such that

$$\log(E(Y_{ijk})/c_{ijk}) = \gamma_l + \tau_{li} + \beta_{lj} \quad (2.1)$$

where γ_l is the overall mean of gene l normalized expression level; on gene l expression, τ_{li} is the i -th treatment effect such that $\sum_i \tau_{li} = 0$; β_{lj} is the j -th block effect such that $\sum_j \beta_{lj} = 0$; the total number of copies on each sequencing device c_{ijk} is known as the library size (a priori), Auer and Doerge (2010). Denote $\beta_l = [\gamma_l, \tau_{l1}, \dots, \tau_{l(a-1)}, \beta_{l1}, \dots, \beta_{l(b-1)}]'$, $l = 1, \dots, g$. Let N be the total number of observations for each gene.

We apply the Newton Raphson method of Wedderburn (1974) to obtain the maximum likelihood estimation of the parameters in (2.1) given by $\hat{\gamma}_l$, $\hat{\tau}_{li}$, and $\hat{\beta}_{lj}$, $i = 1, \dots, a$, $j =$

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$1, \dots, b$ for each $l, l = 1, \dots, g$ respectively. We have that $\widehat{\beta}_l = [\widehat{\gamma}_l, \widehat{\tau}_{l1}, \dots, \widehat{\tau}_{l(a-1)}, \widehat{\beta}_{l1}, \dots, \widehat{\beta}_{l(b-1)}]'$, $l = 1, \dots, g$.

Since the expression level of gene l may present over-dispersion, we use the plug-in estimation of ϕ_l in Wedderburn (1974) that

$$\widehat{\phi}_l = \left(\sum_{i,j,k} \frac{(Y_{lijk} - \exp\{(\widehat{\gamma}_l + \widehat{\tau}_{li} + \widehat{\beta}_{lj}) + \log(c_{ijk})\})^2}{\exp\{(\widehat{\gamma}_l + \widehat{\tau}_{li} + \widehat{\beta}_{lj}) + \log(c_{ijk})\}} \right) / (N - (a + b - 1)),$$

Auer and Doerge (2010) and Li (2020, 2021).

We focus on testing the hypotheses for all pairwise comparisons in association to the treatment effects that

$$H_{0_{l,ii'}} : \tau_{li} - \tau_{li'} = 0 \text{ vs. } H_{1_{l,ii'}} : \tau_{li} - \tau_{li'} \neq 0, \quad (2.2)$$

$i \neq i' = 1, \dots, a$, for gene $l = 1, \dots, g$.

Let the $\binom{a}{2} \times (a + b - 1)$ contrast matrix in association to the hypotheses in (2.2) be C in such a way that $C\beta_l = \mathbf{0}$, $l = 1, \dots, g$ is equivalent to $\cap_{i \neq i'} H_{0_{l,ii'}}$. We use the root for inference given by

$$\mathbf{T}_l = (\widehat{\phi}_l \widehat{\Delta}_l)^{-1} (C\widehat{\beta}_l - C\beta_l), \quad (2.3)$$

for gene $l = 1, \dots, g$; $\widehat{\Delta}_l$ is a $\binom{a}{2} \times \binom{a}{2}$ diagonal matrix whose diagonal elements equal to the diagonal elements in $C(X'\widehat{W}_l X)C'$ in order; X is the design matrix for (2.1); \widehat{W}_l is an $N \times N$ diagonal weight matrix with the diagonal elements given by the estimation of $\{E(Y_{lijk})\}$ based on $\widehat{\beta}_l$, see page 156 of Li (2020).

Let $\mathbf{T} = [\mathbf{T}'_1, \dots, \mathbf{T}'_a]'$. Let q_α be the upper $\alpha/2 - th$ quantile of the joint distribution of \mathbf{T} . Since the joint distribution of \mathbf{T} is unknown in general, we approximate the quantile q_α based on the parametric bootstrap method, Li (2020). That is, for each bootstrap r , $r = 1, \dots, B$ we generate the random observations $\{Y_{lijk}^{(r)}\}$ from the Poisson distribution with mean $\exp(\log(c_{lijk}) + \widehat{\gamma}_l + \widehat{\tau}_{li} + \widehat{\beta}_{lj})$; for each i, j , and l , compute the maximum likelihood estimation $\widehat{\gamma}_l^{(r)}$, $\widehat{\tau}_{li}^{(r)}$, and $\widehat{\beta}_{lj}^{(r)}$ based on the bootstrap observations $\{Y_{lijk}^{(r)}\}$; hence, we can compute $\mathbf{T}^{(r)}$; obtain the $r - th$ bootstrap maximum modulus statistic $T_M^{(r)} = \max(|\mathbf{T}^{(r)}|)$. We choose the upper $\alpha - th$ quantile of the sampling distribution of $T_M^{(r)}$ as the bootstrap approximation of q_α . For details, see page 158 of Li (2020).

We have that a $(1 - \alpha)100\%$ simultaneous confidence interval of $C\beta_l$ is given by

$$[C\widehat{\beta}_l - q_\alpha(\widehat{\phi}_l \widehat{\Delta}_l \mathbf{1})^{1/2}, C\widehat{\beta}_l + q_\alpha(\widehat{\phi}_l \widehat{\Delta}_l \mathbf{1})^{1/2}], \quad (2.4)$$

$l = 1, \dots, g$ where $\mathbf{1}$ is a $\binom{a}{2} \times 1$ vector of 1's.

Under the complete null hypothesis $\cap_{l, i \neq i'} H_{0_{l,ii'}}$, the test statistic based on the root in (2.3) is given by

$$\mathbf{T}_{l,0} = (\widehat{\phi}_l \widehat{\Delta}_l)^{-1} C\widehat{\beta}_l, \quad (2.5)$$

for each $l, l = 1, \dots, g$.

We have that a simultaneous level- α test for $H_{0_{l,ii'}}$ in (2.2) versus its two-sided alternative is given by rejecting $H_{0_{l,ii'}}$, if the corresponding element in $|\mathbf{T}_{l,0}| > q_\alpha$, $l = 1, \dots, g$.

3. Simulation Study

Bottomly et al (2011) evaluated the striatum gene expression levels between two inbred mouse strains C57BL/6J and DBA/2J using a RNA sequencing experiment. Let the strain be the treatment effect in this study that C57BL/6J and DBA/2J are coded as treatment 1 and 2 in (2.1), respectively. Since there are 3 flow-cells in the experiment, we consider the flow-cell as the block effect that the flow-cell j attributes the j -th block effect in (2.1), $j = 1, 2, 3$. The total number of observations $N = 21$ for each gene. There are $g = 12839$ genes in total. The data is from the database “<http://bowtie-bio.sourceforge.net/recount/>”. See Bottomly et al (2011) and Li (2021) for details of the experimental design.

We conduct a pilot simulation study based on the gene expressions from the first 30 genes in the dataset. More specifically, we assume that the data fit to (2.1). We compute the maximum likelihood estimation of the parameters in (2.1). To illustrate the simultaneous inference for all pairwise comparisons, we raise the number of treatments to 3 using the design in Table 1 for all l . Under the complete null hypothesis in (2.2), we assign 0 to all treatment effects, for $l = 1, \dots, 30$. For each simulation, we obtain the observations $\{Y_{ljk}\}$ from the Poisson distribution with mean $\exp(\log(c_{ljk}) + \hat{\gamma}_l + \hat{\beta}_{lj})$ where $\hat{\gamma}_l$ and $\hat{\beta}_{lj}$ are the maximum likelihood estimation based on the real data. To the Poisson observations above, we add a sequence of Gaussian noise (rounded to the closest integer) with mean 0 's and variance proportional to the mean response above with the proportions equal to $[0.1, 0.2, \dots, 2.1]'$, following the order in Table 1. Finally, we round the observation to 0.01, if it is less or equal to 0.

For each simulation, we compute the test statistic (2.5); estimate q_α based on $B = 400$ bootstrap datasets; conduct the simultaneous test in section 2 at the nominal significance level $\alpha = 0.05$. We compute the familywise error rate based on 1,000 simulations. It shows that the $FWER = 0.027$, which is well below the nominal level 0.05. We compute the expected value of the bootstrap estimation of $q_{0.05}$ and it equals 8.866. Based on the above mechanism to generate data, we compute the “real” quantile $q_{0.05, sim.}$ of the sampling distribution of $T_M = \max(|\mathbf{T}_l|)$ based on 10,000 simulated datasets. It shows that $q_{0.05, sim.} = 4.049$, which is considerably below the expected value of the bootstrap estimation of $q_{0.05}$. As a result, the simultaneous test based on parametric bootstrapping provides a conservative test in this simulation study.

Note that in the simulation study of Li (2020), the simultaneous test in section 2 controls the $FWER$ at the nominal level, over a range of over-dispersion configurations. Hence, a pilot simulation study is recommended before applying the simultaneous test based on parametric bootstrapping. Analogously, since the overall coverage probability equals $1 - FWER$, the simultaneous confidence intervals using the parametric bootstrap method in section 2 has the overall coverage probability 0.973, which largely exceeds the nominal level 0.95. The author is currently investigating a robust alternative of the simultaneous inference based on parametric bootstrapping in RNA sequencing gene expressions analysis.

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Table 1: The Experimental Design of the Simulation Study

Experimental Unit	Treatment	Block
1	1	1
2	2	1
3	3	1
4	1	2
5	2	2
6	3	2
7	1	2
8	2	3
9	3	3
10	1	3
11	2	1
12	3	1
13	1	1
14	2	1
15	3	2
16	1	2
17	2	2
18	3	3
19	1	3
20	2	3
21	3	3